

A Response-Surface Framework for Empirical Modeling of Nonlinear Color Enhancement Operators in HSL Space

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Abstract

This work presents a data-driven framework for empirically characterizing nonlinear color enhancement operators through controlled measurements in HSL space. The approach combines synthetic probe images, response-surface fitting, and structured residual analysis to derive explicit functional approximations of operator behavior without assuming access to internal implementation details. As a case study, we apply the framework to a widely used commercial Vibrance adjustment and measure how the induced saturation and lightness variations depend on initial saturation, hue, and lightness. The analysis first yields a two-dimensional chromatic surface, $\Delta S = F(S, H)$, represented by a truncated Fourier expansion in hue with saturation-dependent coefficients. Residual diagnostics on real images then reveal systematic lightness effects not captured by a purely chromatic model, motivating an extended three-dimensional formulation in which both saturation and lightness increments depend on (S, H, L) . The final model is validated on hold-out synthetic data and on real photographic examples, where it reproduces the dominant smooth component of the transformation with substantially reduced reconstruction error. Beyond the specific case study, the proposed framework provides an explicit and reproducible methodology for empirical modeling of complex color transformations and for identifying when higher-dimensional structure is required.

Keywords: vibrance adjustment; color image enhancement; response surface modeling; HSL color space; chromatic–lightness coupling; Fourier modeling.

1 Introduction

Color enhancement is a fundamental operation in digital imaging and photographic post-production. In addition to global saturation controls, modern editing systems include selective adjustments designed to modify chromatic intensity in a content-dependent way across hue, saturation, and brightness regimes. Such operators are widely used in practice, yet their functional behavior is often difficult to analyze because they are nonlinear, multidimensional, and available only as black-box transformations.

From a methodological perspective, this raises a broader problem: how can one empirically characterize a complex color operator when its internal implementation is unknown or inaccessible? Existing literature on hue-preserving enhancement has mainly focused on algorithm design in RGB space, geometric constructions in the color cube, or global descriptive statistics such as mean saturation. By contrast, explicit empirical response-surface models that quantify how chromatic and lightness increments depend jointly on color coordinates remain rare.

The objective of this work is to develop and demonstrate a data-driven framework for empirical modeling of nonlinear color enhancement operators in HSL space. Rather than assuming a specific internal mechanism, we treat the operator as a black-box transformation and infer its behavior through controlled probe images in which only one variable—initial saturation S , hue H , or lightness L —varies at a time. This allows the dominant functional dependencies to be isolated and represented explicitly.

As a case study, we apply this framework to the Vibrance adjustment implemented in Adobe Photoshop, a widely used operator in photographic workflows. The role of this case study is twofold: first, it provides a practically relevant example of a nonlinear color transformation; second, it serves as a testbed for assessing whether the proposed methodology can recover a compact and predictive response-surface representation from measurements alone.

Our first goal is structural and descriptive: to determine whether the induced saturation variation can be represented by separable or low-dimensional forms, and to derive an explicit approximation of the dominant chromatic response. This leads to a two-dimensional empirical surface of the form

$$\Delta S = F(S, H),$$

in which hue periodicity is represented through truncated Fourier expansions with saturation-dependent coefficients.

Our second goal is diagnostic and constructive: to evaluate how far such a chromatic model remains predictive on real images and to determine what structure is missing when it fails. Structured residual analysis reveals systematic lightness discrepancies not explained by a purely chromatic description, which motivates extending the representation to a three-dimensional formulation in which both saturation and lightness increments depend jointly on (S, H, L) .

The resulting contribution is therefore not limited to a single photographic adjustment. More generally, the paper proposes a reproducible workflow for empirical response-surface modeling of black-box color operators, combining controlled probing, compact functional approximation, hold-out validation, and residual diagnostics to guide model extension when low-dimensional descriptions are insufficient.

1.1 Related Work

Color image enhancement methods that preserve hue while modifying luminance or saturation have been extensively studied in the image processing literature. A central difficulty in this class of methods is to enhance contrast or saturation without introducing hue shifts or violating the RGB gamut constraints.

A foundational contribution in this direction is the work of Naik and Murthy [1], who proposed a hue-preserving color image enhancement method based on intensity transformation in RGB space. Their approach modifies pixel intensity through a scalar transformation while maintaining the direction of the RGB vector, thereby preserving hue. Although effective in avoiding gamut problems, it was later observed that this method may reduce saturation in certain luminance regimes.

To address this limitation, Yang and Lee [2] introduced a modified hue-preserving gamut mapping strategy. They partitioned the RGB space according to luminance levels and applied different transformations to dark, mid-tone, and bright colors. While this approach increases saturation in some regions of the luminance range, colors in the mid-luminance band remain governed by Naik and Murthy’s formulation, and saturation improvement is not guaranteed across all chromatic configurations.

Further refinement was proposed by Yu et al. [3], who introduced a geometric projection method in the RGB cube. In their approach, each color vector is projected onto one of three bisecting planes of the RGB cube before applying a luminance transformation. This construction increases the distance from the intensity axis and therefore increases saturation while preserving

hue and avoiding gamut violations. Experimental results reported in that work show improved mean saturation compared to both Naik and Yang–Lee methods. However, the method remains algorithmic and geometric in nature, and does not provide an explicit functional characterization of saturation variation as a function of chromatic coordinates.

More recently, Inoue et al. [4] proposed an extended hue-preserving saturation improvement framework, also formulated geometrically within the RGB cube. Their method analyzes chromatic transformations through projections and luminance-controlled mappings, and provides comparative evaluation across several benchmark images. While the study advances the geometric understanding of saturation enhancement under hue preservation constraints, it does not derive an explicit parametric model of the induced saturation change in perceptual coordinates such as HSL or HSV.

Other related approaches include three-dimensional histogram equalization techniques [5], which reinterpret hue-preserving enhancement from a joint color-distribution perspective, but similarly do not yield an explicit analytic model of the transformation in chromatic coordinates.

Importantly, the existing literature focuses primarily on algorithm design in RGB space and on qualitative or mean-statistic evaluations (e.g., mean saturation). Based on the works we could identify in the open literature, we did not find prior studies that provide: (i) an empirical functional model of saturation variation expressed explicitly as a continuous function of saturation and hue, (ii) a quantitative surface representation of the transformation induced by a commercial image editing operator, or (iii) a structured error analysis that decomposes chromatic and lightness contributions on real images.

More generally, the literature does not appear to provide a unified framework that combines controlled probing, explicit response-surface reconstruction, and residual-based model refinement for black-box color enhancement operators. Commercial adjustments such as Vibrance provide a practically relevant test case for such a framework, because they are widely used, nonlinear, and not described in parametric form in the open literature. This gap motivates the present study, which adopts a data-driven functional modeling approach aimed not only at a specific operator, but also at establishing a reproducible methodology for empirical characterization of complex color transformations.

2 Materials and Methods

The main contribution of this work is methodological as well as empirical. Beyond the specific case study considered here, the results show that a black-box color enhancement operator can be characterized through a combination of controlled synthetic probes, explicit response-surface fitting, and structured residual diagnostics. The Photoshop Vibrance adjustment serves as a representative example through which the strengths and limitations of this framework can be assessed quantitatively.

The modeling strategy proceeds through a sequence of progressively richer models. For clarity we assign a specific name to each formulation used in the study.

1. Separable model.

The first hypothesis assumes that the chromatic response factorizes into independent functions of saturation and hue:

$$\Delta S(S, H) \approx a(S) w(H).$$

In this formulation the function $a(S)$ controls the global strength of the adjustment as a function of the initial saturation, while $w(H)$ represents a fixed hue weighting. This model serves as a structural baseline and is tested experimentally.

2. F model (two-dimensional chromatic surface).

When separability fails, the saturation increment is modeled as a genuine two-dimensional response surface:

$$\Delta S = F(S, H).$$

This surface represents the dominant chromatic component of the Vibrance operator. In the present work $F(S, H)$ is represented by a truncated Fourier expansion in hue with coefficients that depend smoothly on saturation.

3. FG model (chromatic + lightness update).

Residual diagnostics show that the Photoshop output also modifies the lightness channel. An intermediate extension therefore introduces an additional lightness term:

$$\Delta S = F(S, H), \quad \Delta L = G(S, H).$$

Here $F(S, H)$ is the chromatic surface defined above and $G(S, H)$ represents a lightness increment estimated from hue-strip measurements at a fixed lightness level.

4. FGL model (full three-dimensional formulation).

Finally, both increments are allowed to depend explicitly on the input lightness:

$$\Delta S = F(S, H, L), \quad \Delta L = G(S, H, L).$$

This formulation represents the final model used in the paper. It is obtained by estimating the surfaces at several calibration lightness levels and interpolating across L .

The role of this section is to define the experimental protocol and the mathematical form of the models. The empirical validation and quantitative performance of the models are reported separately in Section 3.

2.1 Experimental protocol and measurement

Synthetic test design. To characterize the functional behavior of the Vibrance operator, we perform controlled experiments on synthetic images designed to isolate the dependence of the transformation on the three coordinates of the HSL representation: saturation S , hue H , and lightness L .

Each stimulus is constructed so that only one coordinate varies across the image while the others remain fixed. This allows the operator to be probed along the three principal directions of HSL space without confounding interactions.

The experiments therefore consist of three synthetic tests:

- **Test 1 (saturation ramp).** Hue and lightness are fixed while saturation varies smoothly from low to high values ($S \approx 0 \rightarrow 1$). This test probes the dependence of the operator on the *initial saturation*.
- **Test 2 (hue strip).** Saturation and lightness are fixed ($S = S_0, L = L_0$), while hue spans the full chromatic circle

$$H \in [0, 360).$$

This isolates the dependence of the transformation on *hue*.

- **Test 3 (lightness ramp).** Hue and saturation are fixed while lightness varies from dark to bright values. This probes possible dependence on *lightness*.

Figure 1: Test 1 input image: fixed hue and fixed lightness, with saturation increasing smoothly from low to high values.

Figure 1 illustrates the synthetic image used in Test 1. The image is a horizontal ramp where saturation increases progressively while hue and lightness remain constant.

Figure 2 shows the synthetic stimulus used in Test 2. Here saturation and lightness are fixed while hue varies continuously through the full color circle.

Figure 2: Test 2 input image: fixed saturation and fixed lightness, with hue varying continuously across the full 0° – 360° range.

Figure 3 illustrates the stimulus used in Test 3. In this case hue and saturation remain fixed while lightness increases gradually from dark to bright values.

Figure 3: Test 3 input image: fixed hue and fixed saturation, with lightness increasing from dark to bright.

These tests allow the operator to be sampled along each coordinate axis of the HSL space.

Measurement procedure. For each stimulus we apply the Photoshop Vibrance adjustment and measure the HSL coordinates before and after the transformation.

Let

$$S_{\text{orig}}, \quad S_{\text{new}}, \quad L_{\text{orig}}, \quad L_{\text{new}}$$

denote saturation and lightness before and after the adjustment.

We define the increments

$$\Delta S = S_{\text{new}} - S_{\text{orig}}, \quad \Delta L = L_{\text{new}} - L_{\text{orig}}.$$

Because the stimuli are constructed as horizontal ramps, each column corresponds to a specific value of the controlled variable. A central horizontal scanline is therefore extracted and treated as a one-dimensional discrete sample of the response.

The resulting measurements produce empirical response curves such as

$$\Delta S(H), \quad \Delta S(S), \quad \Delta S(L),$$

which form the basis of the functional modeling described below. All experiments were performed in Adobe Photoshop (version 27.4.0) using 8-bit RGB images in the sRGB working space with Vibrance set to +50 and Saturation set to 0 unless otherwise specified. For the control experiments involving the Hue/Saturation adjustment, we set Saturation to +50 with Vibrance set to 0. All measurements are reported in the HSL convention used by our analysis

pipeline, with $S, L \in [0, 1]$ and $H \in [0, 360)$. RGB values are exported from Photoshop in the sRGB working space and processed by a fixed RGB→HSL conversion implemented in our scripts. Because the workflow uses 8-bit RGB, the measured curves include small staircase artifacts due to quantization and to the nonlinearity of the RGB–HSL mapping; these effects are visible as minor irregularities in the 1D response plots but do not change the dominant smooth structure modeled by the surfaces.

2.2 Testing separability

A natural initial hypothesis is that the chromatic response may be separable in saturation and hue. In a separable model the two variables influence the response independently, meaning that the saturation increment can be written as the product of a saturation term and a hue term:

$$\Delta S(S, H) \approx a(S) w(H). \quad (1)$$

Here $a(S)$ describes how strongly colors are boosted depending on their initial saturation, while $w(H)$ represents a hue-dependent weighting function.

To estimate the hue component we analyze Test 2, in which $S = S_0$ and $L = L_0$ are fixed and hue varies across the full range. The measured response is

$$\Delta S_{T2}(H) = S_{\text{new}}(H) - S_{\text{orig}}(H). \quad (2)$$

Because hue is periodic, we represent it as an angular variable

$$\theta = \frac{2\pi}{360} H. \quad (3)$$

The measured curve is approximated by a truncated Fourier series

$$\Delta S_{T2}(\theta) \approx c_0 + \sum_{k=1}^K (c_k \cos(k\theta) + d_k \sin(k\theta)). \quad (4)$$

If the separability hypothesis were correct, the shape of this hue response would remain invariant when the experiment is repeated at different saturation levels.

To test this prediction we repeat the hue-strip experiment for multiple values of S and compare the normalized curves

$$r(H) = \frac{\Delta S(H)}{\Delta S(H_{\text{ref}})}.$$

where H_{ref} is a fixed reference hue (e.g., $H_{\text{ref}} = 0^\circ$) chosen so that $\Delta S(H_{\text{ref}}) \neq 0$.

The empirical results (reported in Section 3.3) show that these normalized curves do not collapse onto a single profile. Instead, the shape of the hue response varies with S , indicating that hue and saturation interact.

The separable representation is therefore rejected and we proceed to a two-dimensional model.

2.3 Two-dimensional chromatic model (**F model**)

The failure of separability motivates the adoption of the two-dimensional chromatic model introduced above (the **F model**), in which the saturation increment is represented as a genuine response surface

$$\Delta S = F(S, H). \quad (5)$$

Because hue is periodic, we represent the surface using a Fourier expansion in hue with saturation-dependent coefficients.

Let

$$\theta = \frac{2\pi}{360}H.$$

The empirical model is

$$F(S, H) = a_0(S) + \sum_{k=1}^K (a_k(S) \cos(k\theta) + b_k(S) \sin(k\theta)). \quad (6)$$

The coefficients $a_k(S)$ and $b_k(S)$ are modeled as cubic polynomials in saturation:

$$a_k(S) = \alpha_{k,3}S^3 + \alpha_{k,2}S^2 + \alpha_{k,1}S + \alpha_{k,0},$$

$$b_k(S) = \beta_{k,3}S^3 + \beta_{k,2}S^2 + \beta_{k,1}S + \beta_{k,0}.$$

The parameters are estimated in two stages:

1. For each saturation slice S_i , a Fourier series in θ is fitted to the measured curve $\Delta S(H)$.
2. The resulting Fourier coefficients are interpolated across saturation using cubic regression.

The resulting surface provides an explicit empirical approximation

$$\Delta S = F(S, H).$$

The predictive performance of this model on synthetic slices and on real images is evaluated in Section 3.4.

2.4 Intermediate lightness-corrected model (FG)

Real-image diagnostics (Appendix A.1) show that the Photoshop Vibrance operator induces not only saturation changes but also systematic variations in the HSL lightness channel. Before moving to a fully lightness-conditioned three-dimensional formulation, we introduce an intermediate variant that explicitly updates lightness while keeping the chromatic increment independent of L .

We denote this intermediate two-surface variant as the **FG model**. It is defined by

$$\Delta S = F(S, H), \quad \Delta L = G(S, H),$$

so that the reconstruction updates saturation and lightness as

$$\begin{aligned} S_{\text{new}} &= \text{clip}_{[0,1]}(S_{\text{orig}} + F(S_{\text{orig}}, H_{\text{orig}})), \\ L_{\text{new}} &= \text{clip}_{[0,1]}(L_{\text{orig}} + G(S_{\text{orig}}, H_{\text{orig}})), \\ H_{\text{new}} &= H_{\text{orig}}. \end{aligned}$$

Hue variations induced by Vibrance were not measured in this work and assumed negligible compared to saturation and lightness changes; we therefore model the dominant behavior by keeping H unchanged. The function $G(S, H)$ is estimated from hue-strip measurements performed at one fixed reference lightness level (denoted L_{ref}), by measuring ΔL on the same (S, H) sampling grid used for F . The resulting lightness response is then represented using the same Fourier-in-hue structure adopted for F , with coefficients varying smoothly with saturation.

This FG model provides a single- L lightness correction that can improve agreement in specific chromatic regions, but it cannot reproduce lightness-conditioned behavior across different brightness levels; this motivates the final three-dimensional formulation introduced next.

2.5 Three-dimensional extension (FGL model)

Although the surface $F(S, H)$ captures the dominant chromatic structure of the Vibrance operator, the residual analysis described in Appendix A.1 reveals systematic discrepancies that correlate with lightness.

This observation motivates extending the formulation to the full three-dimensional model described above (the **FGL model**).

We therefore introduce two response surfaces

$$\Delta S = F(S, H, L), \quad \Delta L = G(S, H, L).$$

To estimate these functions we repeat the Test 2 calibration procedure at several fixed lightness values

$$L \in \{0.30, 0.50, 0.70\}.$$

For each calibration lightness L_ℓ we fit surfaces

$$\Delta S \approx F_\ell(S, H), \quad \Delta L \approx G_\ell(S, H),$$

using the same Fourier structure described above.

The final three-dimensional functions are obtained by interpolation across lightness:

$$F(S, H, L) = \text{Interp}_L(F_{0.30}, F_{0.50}, F_{0.70}),$$

$$G(S, H, L) = \text{Interp}_L(G_{0.30}, G_{0.50}, G_{0.70}).$$

The resulting model updates both saturation and lightness:

$$\begin{aligned} S_{\text{new}} &= \text{clip}_{[0,1]}(S_{\text{orig}} + F(S_{\text{orig}}, H_{\text{orig}}, L_{\text{orig}})), \\ L_{\text{new}} &= \text{clip}_{[0,1]}(L_{\text{orig}} + G(S_{\text{orig}}, H_{\text{orig}}, L_{\text{orig}})), \\ H_{\text{new}} &= H_{\text{orig}}. \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

The performance of the resulting three-dimensional reconstruction is evaluated on synthetic and real images in Section 3.6.

2.6 Use of AI tools

Large Language Models (LLMs) were used as auxiliary tools during this study.

Figure generation. A LLM was used to assist in generating a subset of schematic/illustrative figures and/or captions. The model was used only to propose layout/text alternatives and to help draft plotting/figure-generation instructions; all figures were produced under the author’s direction and verified against the underlying experimental outputs.

Prompts. Prompts used with the LLM are archived by the author and can be provided upon request. They consisted of requests to (i) propose figure layouts consistent with the reported experiments, (ii) suggest wording for captions aligned with the measured results, and (iii) propose code-agnostic plotting steps (no data fabrication).

3 Results

This section reports the empirical results obtained from the experimental protocol described in Section 2.1.

3.1 Dependence on saturation, hue, and lightness

We begin by analyzing the behavior of the operator along the three coordinate directions of the HSL space. Each experiment uses the synthetic stimuli introduced in Section 2.1.

Saturation (control: Saturation +50, Test 1). We first analyze the behavior of the classical Photoshop Hue/Saturation adjustment with **Saturation = +50**. The measurement is performed on the saturation ramp used in Test 1, where hue and lightness remain fixed and only the initial saturation varies.

Let k denote the (approximately constant) saturation increment induced by the **Saturation = +50** control in the HSL coordinates used in this work. The observed behavior follows an affine rule with clipping:

$$S_{\text{new}} = \min(S + k, 1). \quad (8)$$

Equivalently,

$$\Delta S = \begin{cases} k, & \text{if } S \leq 1 - k, \\ 1 - S, & \text{if } S > 1 - k. \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

This explains why S_{new} follows $S + k$ at low and intermediate saturation values before saturating due to clipping (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Test 1 (saturation ramp), Saturation +50: measured S_{new} versus initial saturation S .

Small irregularities visible in the curve arise from RGB quantization and nonlinear RGB–HSL conversion.

Vibrance (Test 1: saturation ramp). We now apply the **Vibrance** adjustment to the same saturation ramp.

Unlike the classical Saturation mapping control, Vibrance does not apply a constant increment. Instead we observe a nonlinear mapping

$$S_{\text{new}} = S + \phi(S). \quad (10)$$

Equivalently, on the saturation-ramp experiment we have $\Delta S(S) = \phi(S)$ up to clipping at $S = 1$. Here $\phi(S)$ denotes the empirical saturation-dependent increment observed in the saturation ramp experiment; it should not be confused with the separable-model factor $a(S)$ introduced in Section 2.

The measured increment ΔS is small at very low saturation, increases for intermediate values, and decreases again at high saturation before clipping dominates.

This behavior is illustrated in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Test 1 (saturation ramp), Vibrance +50: measured S_{new} versus initial saturation S .

Hue dependence (Test 2: hue strip). To test whether the operator also depends on hue, we analyze the synthetic hue strip described in Section 2.1. Here saturation and lightness remain fixed while hue spans the entire chromatic circle.

If the operator were hue-independent, the output saturation should remain approximately constant across H . Instead, the measured response varies strongly with hue. This behavior is shown in Figure 6.

This confirms that the Vibrance transformation is not purely a function of initial saturation.

Lightness dependence (Test 3: lightness ramp). Finally we analyze the synthetic lightness ramp used in Test 3.

In this test hue and saturation remain fixed while lightness varies. The measured response is shown in Figure 7.

The variation of S_{new} across the midrange of lightness is small, suggesting that the dominant dependence of the operator is chromatic rather than luminance-based. However, as shown later, subtle lightness–chromatic interactions become visible in real-image experiments.

Figure 6: Test 2 (hue strip), Vibrance +50: measured S_{new} versus hue H .

Figure 7: Test 3 (lightness ramp), Vibrance +50: measured S_{new} versus lightness L .

3.2 Baseline validation (Saturation control)

To verify that the experimental procedure itself does not introduce artificial hue or lightness dependencies, we repeat Tests 2 and 3 using the classical Saturation control.

On the hue strip, Saturation +50 produces an essentially flat response across hue. On the lightness ramp, the response is also approximately constant across the midrange of lightness. The corresponding control responses are shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Control tests, Saturation +50. Top: hue strip. Bottom: lightness ramp.

These results confirm that the classical Saturation adjustment behaves as a global additive

mapping independent of hue and lightness.

3.3 Testing separability

Following the modeling strategy described in Section 2, we next test whether the chromatic response can be approximated by a separable function

$$\Delta S(S, H) \approx a(S) w(H).$$

If separability held, the normalized hue responses measured at different saturation levels would collapse onto a single curve.

Instead, the normalized curves differ significantly, as shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Non-separability test: normalized hue response $r(H)$ changes with initial saturation.

To verify this behavior directly at the measurement level, we repeat the hue-strip experiment at several saturation values

$$S \in \{0.1, 0.3, 0.5, 0.7, 0.9\}.$$

The resulting curves $\Delta S(H)$ are shown in Figure 10.

The shape of the hue response clearly changes with saturation, confirming that Vibrance cannot be represented by a separable model.

3.4 Two-dimensional chromatic model (F model)

Given the failure of separability, we adopt the two-dimensional chromatic surface defined in Section 2 (the **F model**)

Figure 10: Measured hue response for multiple initial saturation levels.

$$\Delta S = F(S, H).$$

The fitted surface obtained from the synthetic measurements is shown in Figure 11.

Figure 11: Estimated surface $F(S, H) = \Delta S$ for Vibrance = +50.

To illustrate the behavior more clearly, Figure 12 shows model slices $\Delta S(H)$ at selected saturation levels.

Figure 12: Model slices $\Delta S(H)$ at selected values of S .

Figure 13 compares the measured curves with the model predictions.

Figure 13: Observed (solid) versus model (dashed) slices at selected training saturations.

Hold-out validation. To evaluate generalization we test the model on a saturation slice $S = 0.55$ that was excluded during fitting.

Figure 14: Hold-out validation at $S = 0.55$: observed $\Delta S(H)$ versus model prediction.

Figure 15: Residual $r(H)$ at $S = 0.55$.

The validation error is comparable to the training error (RMSE = 0.068 in validation versus 0.053 on the training slices), indicating that the surface captures the dominant smooth component of the transformation.

Real-image validation. We next apply the chromatic surface to a real photographic image by performing the update

$$S_{\text{new}} = \text{clip}_{[0,1]}(S_{\text{orig}} + F(S_{\text{orig}}, H_{\text{orig}})).$$

Figure 16: Real-image application of the chromatic $F(S, H)$ model (original, Photoshop output, model reconstruction, and error visualization).

The quantitative reconstruction error of the purely chromatic model is summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Reconstruction error for the chromatic F model.

Metric	Value
RMSE RGB	10.2834 (4.03%)
MAE RGB	6.9957 (2.74%)
MaxAbs RGB	43.0 (16.86%)

The remaining discrepancy motivates the extensions introduced below.

3.5 Lightness-corrected model (FG)

The intermediate FG model introduced in Section 2.4 augments the chromatic surface with a lightness increment calibrated at a single reference lightness level:

$$\Delta S = F(S, H), \quad \Delta L = G(S, H).$$

Applying this model to the real-image reconstruction yields the error metrics summarized in Table 2.

Table 2: Reconstruction error for the intermediate FG model.

Metric	Value
RMSE RGB	11.6115 (4.55%)
MAE RGB	9.9226 (3.89%)
MaxAbs RGB	40.0 (15.69%)

Although this formulation partially compensates for lightness discrepancies in specific chromatic regions, the global reconstruction error slightly increases compared to the purely chromatic model.

3.6 Three-dimensional reconstruction (FGL model)

We therefore extend the FG formulation by allowing both increments to depend explicitly on lightness, leading to the full three-dimensional model described in Section 2.

The resulting model is

$$\Delta S = F(S, H, L), \quad \Delta L = G(S, H, L).$$

Calibration is performed at three lightness levels

$$L \in \{0.30, 0.50, 0.70\},$$

and the surfaces are interpolated across lightness.

Figures 17 and 18 show the resulting fitted surfaces.

Figure 17: Estimated saturation increment surfaces $F_\ell(S, H)$ at three lightness levels.

Figure 18: Estimated lightness increment surfaces $G_\ell(S, H)$ at three lightness levels.

The real-image reconstruction using this final model is shown in Figure 19.

To clarify the progression of the models introduced in Section 2, we compare three variants: the chromatic **F model**, the intermediate **FG model** (defined in Section 2.4), and the final three-dimensional **FGL model**. The quantitative comparison is summarized in Table 3. All

Figure 19: Real-image application of the final three-dimensional model.

Table 3: Global reconstruction error for the three model variants. RGB errors are reported both in raw RGB units and as percentage of the full RGB range (0–255).

Metric	F	FG	FGL
RMSE RGB	10.2834 (4.03%)	11.6115 (4.55%)	5.8205 (2.28%)
MAE RGB	6.9957 (2.74%)	9.9226 (3.89%)	4.5505 (1.78%)
MaxAbs RGB	43.0 (16.86%)	40.0 (15.69%)	25.0 (9.80%)

RGB errors are reported both in absolute RGB units and as percentage of the full RGB dynamic range (0–255), which facilitates interpretation of the reconstruction accuracy.

The inclusion of lightness dependence reduces the reconstruction error substantially, confirming that the Vibrance operator is best described by a three-dimensional response surface.

4 Discussion

4.1 From structural observation to predictive modeling

The main contribution of this work is methodological as well as empirical. Beyond the specific case study considered here, the results show that a black-box color enhancement operator can be characterized through a combination of controlled synthetic probes, explicit response-surface fitting, and structured residual diagnostics. The Photoshop Vibrance adjustment serves as a representative example through which the strengths and limitations of this framework can be assessed quantitatively.

The experiments reveal a clear progression of model complexity and predictive capability. The successive models introduced in Section 2 represent increasingly realistic approximations of the operator:

- the purely chromatic two-dimensional surface $F(S, H)$,
- the intermediate lightness-corrected formulation FG ,

- and the final three-dimensional model *FGL*.

This progression is summarized in Table 3. Two important conclusions emerge from this comparison.

First, the purely chromatic model $F(S, H)$ already captures the dominant structure of the Vibrance transformation. Even though the operator is highly nonlinear, a compact Fourier representation with saturation-dependent coefficients reproduces the main chromatic behavior with moderate reconstruction error.

Second, the largest improvement occurs when lightness dependence is introduced explicitly. The final *FGL* model reduces the RGB reconstruction error by roughly a factor of two compared to the purely chromatic formulation. This indicates that the Vibrance operator cannot be fully described as a chromatic adjustment alone.

4.2 Non-separability of hue and saturation

The experiments on synthetic strips establish that the chromatic response is intrinsically two-dimensional.

Figures 9 and 10 show that the hue response changes shape as the initial saturation varies. If the operator were separable, normalized hue responses measured at different saturation levels would collapse onto a single curve. Instead, the curves differ substantially.

This observation rejects models of the form

$$\Delta S(S, H) \approx a(S) w(H),$$

and implies that hue and saturation interact directly. In practical terms, Vibrance does not apply a fixed hue mask modulated by a saturation gain; the protection or enhancement of a given hue depends on how saturated that hue already is.

This interaction motivates modeling the chromatic response as a genuine surface

$$\Delta S = F(S, H).$$

4.3 Smooth backbone of the chromatic response

Despite the intrinsic non-separability, the empirical surface exhibits a strong smooth component.

The Fourier representation adopted in the F model captures:

- the global shape of the hue response,
- the location of chromatic maxima and minima,
- the dependence of amplitude on saturation,
- and the overall structure of the response surface.

Hold-out validation at $S = 0.55$ confirms that the fitted surface generalizes to unseen saturation levels and is not merely interpolating the training slices.

However, the model does not reproduce certain plateau-like regions and sharp transitions visible in the measured curves. These features likely arise from internal conditional logic in the algorithm and cannot be represented by low-order smooth basis functions.

The resulting interpretation is that Vibrance contains a dominant smooth chromatic backbone combined with additional non-smooth mechanisms.

4.4 Role of lightness in the operator

The error diagnostics reported in Appendix A reveal that the residual mismatch of the chromatic model is strongly structured across hue and saturation and correlates with systematic changes in the HSL lightness channel.

Two observations support this conclusion:

- the Photoshop output produces a measurable lightness increment ΔL ,
- residual errors of the chromatic model concentrate in chromatic regions where lightness shifts are strongest.

Introducing the intermediate FG model, which adds a lightness increment calibrated at a single reference lightness level, improves agreement in some chromatic regions but does not reduce the global error.

In contrast, calibrating the surfaces at multiple lightness levels and interpolating across brightness leads to the full three-dimensional formulation

$$\Delta S = F(S, H, L), \quad \Delta L = G(S, H, L),$$

which significantly improves reconstruction accuracy (Table 3). The reduction of RGB RMSE from about 10.3 to 5.8 demonstrates that lightness dependence is a key structural component of the Vibrance operator.

4.5 Interpretation of the remaining residual

Even the three-dimensional model does not perfectly reproduce the Photoshop output. The remaining discrepancy is not random noise but a structured residual localized in specific chromatic regions.

The spectral analysis in Appendix A shows that this residual energy is concentrated in low-frequency harmonics, indicating that the mismatch is not primarily due to insufficient Fourier resolution. While this evidence disfavors a purely high-frequency explanation, it does not exclude additional non-Fourier nonlinearities (e.g., conditional gating) in the proprietary implementation.

This suggests that the internal Vibrance algorithm likely includes mechanisms such as:

- hue-dependent thresholds,
- piecewise definitions across chromatic sectors,
- or saturation-dependent gating functions.

The smooth surfaces developed in this work therefore represent an explicit approximation of the dominant continuous component of the transformation rather than a complete reconstruction of its internal logic.

4.6 Implications

The results support three broader conclusions.

First, complex black-box image adjustments can be characterized empirically without direct access to their implementation, provided that the probing stimuli are designed to isolate interpretable coordinates and that the measured responses are represented through explicit low-dimensional surfaces.

Second, structured residual analysis is not merely a post hoc error check but an effective methodological tool for model refinement. In the present case, it identifies the point at which

a purely chromatic description becomes insufficient and motivates the transition to a three-dimensional formulation.

Third, the same workflow used here is not specific to the Photoshop Vibrance adjustment. The combination of synthetic probing, response-surface reconstruction, hold-out validation, and residual diagnostics can in principle be transferred to other photographic controls, color-enhancement operators, or camera-processing pipelines whenever the goal is to obtain an explicit empirical approximation of a nonlinear transformation.

In this sense, the case study serves as a concrete demonstration of a more general empirical modeling strategy for color transformations rather than as an isolated reverse-engineering exercise.

4.7 Scope and limitations

This study provides an empirical characterization of a specific commercial operator under a controlled configuration (Photoshop 27.4.0, sRGB working space, 8-bit RGB exports, Vibrance = +50, Saturation = 0). The resulting surfaces should therefore be interpreted as a response-surface approximation of that configuration rather than as a universal model of “vibrance” across software, versions, or color-management settings.

Moreover, HSL is adopted here because it provides an interpretable coordinate system aligned with common photographic controls and enables direct visualization of chromatic dependencies via (S, H, L) . HSL is not perceptually uniform; therefore, the fitted coefficients should not be interpreted as perceptual distances, but as an operational description of how the measured HSL coordinates change under the operator.

5 Conclusion

This work presents a data-driven framework for empirical response-surface modeling of nonlinear color enhancement operators in HSL space and demonstrates it on a widely used Vibrance adjustment.

Controlled synthetic experiments show that the transformation differs fundamentally from a classical saturation adjustment. The operator exhibits nonlinear and hue-dependent behavior in which the chromatic response changes shape as the initial saturation varies. This observation rejects separable formulations and motivates the representation of the saturation increment as a two-dimensional surface

$$\Delta S = F(S, H).$$

A compact Fourier-based model captures the dominant chromatic structure of this response. Structured residual analysis on real images then shows that a purely chromatic description is insufficient, because the operator also induces systematic lightness changes correlated with specific chromatic regions. This motivates the extension to a three-dimensional formulation

$$\Delta S = F(S, H, L), \quad \Delta L = G(S, H, L).$$

Quantitative validation shows that this extended model substantially improves reconstruction accuracy relative to the purely chromatic formulation, indicating that lightness–chromatic coupling is a key structural component of the transformation.

Beyond the specific case study, the main outcome of the work is methodological: the paper shows how controlled probing, explicit response-surface fitting, and structured residual diagnostics can be combined into a reproducible framework for empirical characterization of black-box color operators. The resulting models provide compact and interpretable approximations of the dominant smooth component of such transformations, while the residual structure indicates where additional conditional or non-smooth mechanisms may remain outside the scope of low-order surface models.

A Error analysis and model extensions

The main Results section establishes the empirical behavior of the Vibrance operator and presents the response-surface models introduced in Section 2. In particular:

- Section 3.4 evaluates the chromatic **F model**

$$\Delta S = F(S, H),$$

- the intermediate **FG model** (defined in Section 2.4) augments the chromatic surface with a lightness update calibrated at a single reference lightness:

$$\Delta S = F(S, H), \quad \Delta L = G(S, H),$$

- Section 3.6 introduces and validates the final three-dimensional **FGL model**

$$\Delta S = F(S, H, L), \quad \Delta L = G(S, H, L).$$

The purpose of this appendix is different. Rather than introducing new models, it provides a detailed technical analysis of the residual mismatch between Photoshop Vibrance and the reconstructed surfaces. The diagnostics reported here explain the origin of the discrepancies observed in the Results section and motivate the transition from the chromatic model to the final three-dimensional formulation.

A.1 Residual Diagnostics (real image)

The real-image validation reported in Section 3.4 provides global error metrics (RMSE, MAE, maximum error) but these scalar values alone do not explain *where* the residual mismatch occurs.

This appendix therefore analyzes the spatial and chromatic structure of the error through several complementary diagnostics:

- RGB clipping analysis,
- boundary proximity tests,
- error localization over saturation and hue,
- distribution of per-pixel errors,
- spectral analysis of synthetic residuals.

All diagnostics refer to the same landscape image used in the Results section (Figure 19).

A.2 Residual diagnostics for the chromatic model

To evaluate whether the mismatch could be reduced by increasing the harmonic resolution of the model, we repeated the real-image reconstruction using a Fourier order $K = 12$ instead of $K = 6$ while keeping the same cubic interpolation in S .

The quantitative comparison between the two models (computed in RGB space, values in $[0, 255]$) is:

- $K = 6$: RMSE = 10.2834 (4.03% of full scale), MAE = 6.9957 (2.74%).
- $K = 12$: RMSE = 10.31 (4.04%), MAE = 6.437 (2.52%).

The increase in Fourier order does not produce a meaningful reduction of the reconstruction error.

The spatial structure of the error remains essentially unchanged, indicating that the discrepancy is not primarily due to insufficient Fourier resolution in hue.

Figure 20: Real-image application of the empirical model with $K = 12$.

A.3 Global error metrics

Let $I_{\text{PS}}(x)$ denote the Photoshop output and $I_{\text{M}}(x)$ the model reconstruction. The per-pixel RGB difference is defined as

$$\Delta I(x) = I_{\text{PS}}(x) - I_{\text{M}}(x).$$

From this we compute global reconstruction metrics:

$$\text{RMSE}_{\text{RGB}} = \sqrt{\mathbb{E}[\|\Delta I(x)\|_2^2]}/3,$$

$$\text{MAE}_{\text{RGB}} = \mathbb{E}[|\Delta I(x)|],$$

$$\text{MaxAbs}_{\text{RGB}} = \max_{x,c} |\Delta I_c(x)|.$$

In addition we compare the saturation channels in HSL space:

$$\Delta S(x) = S_{\text{PS}}(x) - S_{\text{M}}(x).$$

These scalar metrics quantify the magnitude of the discrepancy but do not explain its origin.

A.4 Clipping analysis

Because both images are stored in 8-bit RGB, we investigate whether reconstruction errors arise from differences in hard RGB clipping.

A pixel is defined as clipped when one channel reaches an extreme value:

$$\min(R, G, B) = 0 \quad \text{or} \quad \max(R, G, B) = 255.$$

The clipping status is evaluated independently for Photoshop and model outputs. A visual comparison of clipping status between Photoshop and the model is reported in Figure 22.

Although clipping differences exist, they do not dominate the reconstruction error.

Global error metrics — real_example_1 (Photoshop vs Model)

metric	value
RMSE RGB (0-255)	10.2834 (4.033% of 0-255)
MAE RGB (0-255)	6.99569 (2.743% of 0-255)
MaxAbs RGB (0-255)	43 (16.863% of 0-255)
RMSE HLS saturation (0-1)	0.103471 (10.347% of 0-1)
MAE HLS saturation (0-1)	0.0828958 (8.290% of 0-1)
MaxAbs HLS saturation (0-1)	0.448456 (44.846% of 0-1)

Figure 21: Global error metrics for the landscape example.

Figure 22: RGB clipping comparison between Photoshop and model outputs.

A.5 Boundary proximity test

We also test whether errors are concentrated near the RGB gamut boundary.

Pixels are classified according to the original image $I_0(x)$:

$$\min(I_0(x)) \leq \tau \quad \text{or} \quad \max(I_0(x)) \geq 255 - \tau.$$

Figure 23 reports the counts of pixels near the RGB boundary under this criterion.

The corresponding error comparison between boundary and non-boundary pixels is shown in Figure 24.

The analysis shows that proximity to the RGB boundary does not explain the majority of the reconstruction error.

A.6 Error distribution across saturation and hue

To localize the residual mismatch in chromatic space we compute the per-pixel RGB magnitude error

$$e(x) = \sqrt{(\Delta R)^2 + (\Delta G)^2 + (\Delta B)^2}.$$

Pixels are then aggregated into bins according to their original saturation or hue. Error statistics aggregated by saturation bin are shown in Figure 25.

Figure 23: Counts of pixels near the RGB boundary.

Figure 24: Error comparison between boundary and non-boundary pixels.

The associated energy share by saturation bin is shown in Figure 26.

Error statistics aggregated by hue bin are shown in Figure 27.

The associated energy share by hue bin is shown in Figure 28.

The residual is strongly structured across hue and saturation, indicating systematic modeling mismatch rather than random noise.

A.7 Distribution of per-pixel errors

The distribution of per-pixel RGB errors is shown in Figure 29.

The distribution exhibits a dominant bulk with structured secondary components in the tail, confirming that the mismatch is localized to specific chromatic regions.

Figure 25: Error statistics aggregated by saturation bin.

Figure 26: Energy share of the error by saturation bin.

A.8 Spectral analysis of residual structure

To determine whether the residual mismatch is primarily high-frequency in hue, we analyze synthetic hue-strip slices.

For each saturation slice S_0 we compute the residual

$$r_{S_0}(H) = \Delta S_{\text{obs}}(H; S_0) - \Delta S_{\text{model}}(H; S_0).$$

The discrete Fourier transform of the residual is

$$\hat{r}_{S_0}(k) = \sum_{j=0}^{N-1} r_{S_0}(H_j) e^{-2\pi i k j / N}.$$

Figure 30 summarizes the residual magnitude across saturation slices.

Figure 27: Error aggregated by hue bin.

Figure 28: Energy share by hue bin.

Spectral indicators of the residual are reported in Figure 31.

An overlay of normalized residual spectra across slices is shown in Figure 32.

The residual energy concentrates in low-frequency harmonics, indicating that increasing Fourier order alone cannot eliminate the discrepancy.

A.9 Evidence of lightness modification

A key observation emerging from the diagnostics is that the Photoshop output also modifies the HSL lightness channel.

Define

$$\Delta L(x) = L_{\text{PS}}(x) - L_{\text{M}}(x).$$

Note that ΔL is measured in the HSL lightness scale in $[0, 1]$ (not in 8-bit RGB units).

Figure 29: Histogram of normalized RGB error magnitude.

Figure 30: Residual magnitude across saturation slices.

Region	mean(ΔL)	RMS(ΔL)
Global image	-0.0188	0.0301
Hue $[180^\circ, 250^\circ]$	-0.0666	0.0676

Table 4: Lightness discrepancy between Photoshop and the chromatic model.

The systematic lightness shift explains a large fraction of the structured residual observed in the Results section.

A.10 Lightness modification on synthetic hue strips

We confirm the existence of lightness changes using synthetic hue strips.

$$\Delta L(H; S_0) = L_{\text{after}}(H; S_0) - L_{\text{before}}(H; S_0).$$

The measured lightness changes on synthetic hue strips are shown in Figure 34.

Figure 31: Spectral indicators of the residual.

Figure 32: Overlay of normalized residual spectra across slices.

The measured curves show that lightness modifications depend smoothly on hue and saturation.

A.11 Transition to the three-dimensional model

The diagnostics presented in this appendix demonstrate that:

- the residual mismatch is structured rather than random,
- the discrepancy cannot be eliminated by increasing Fourier order,
- systematic lightness changes are present in the Photoshop output.

These observations motivate extending the chromatic surface model to a three-dimensional formulation

$$\Delta S = F(S, H, L), \quad \Delta L = G(S, H, L),$$

Figure 33: Distribution of lightness discrepancies.

Figure 34: $\Delta L(H; S_0)$ for synthetic hue strips.

whose calibration and validation are presented in Section 3.6.

B Model coefficients (K=6)

Each Fourier coefficient is modeled as a cubic polynomial:

$$a_k(S) = \alpha_{k,3}S^3 + \alpha_{k,2}S^2 + \alpha_{k,1}S + \alpha_{k,0}, \quad b_k(S) = \beta_{k,3}S^3 + \beta_{k,2}S^2 + \beta_{k,1}S + \beta_{k,0}.$$

The numerical values defining the complete empirical model (K=6) are:

$$\begin{aligned}
(\alpha_{0,3}, \alpha_{0,2}, \alpha_{0,1}, \alpha_{0,0}) &= (-1.807663893, 0.9865249211, 0.7212560711, -0.05225251802). \\
(\alpha_{1,3}, \alpha_{1,2}, \alpha_{1,1}, \alpha_{1,0}) &= (-2.50206288, 4.727060449, -2.4568233, 0.2190624466), \\
(\beta_{1,3}, \beta_{1,2}, \beta_{1,1}, \beta_{1,0}) &= (0.5306306929, -0.9463541708, 0.4687477922, -0.04342341362). \\
(\alpha_{2,3}, \alpha_{2,2}, \alpha_{2,1}, \alpha_{2,0}) &= (1.485980898, -2.054302566, 0.7367761024, -0.06236739579), \\
(\beta_{2,3}, \beta_{2,2}, \beta_{2,1}, \beta_{2,0}) &= (-0.3976512879, 0.763572684, -0.4065358204, 0.03976271232). \\
(\alpha_{3,3}, \alpha_{3,2}, \alpha_{3,1}, \alpha_{3,0}) &= (-0.8291677927, 1.708751695, -0.9486389408, 0.08314493554), \\
(\beta_{3,3}, \beta_{3,2}, \beta_{3,1}, \beta_{3,0}) &= (0.2742248107, -0.353793883, 0.1078697144, -0.005700488122). \\
(\alpha_{4,3}, \alpha_{4,2}, \alpha_{4,1}, \alpha_{4,0}) &= (0.4197530797, -0.5468991399, 0.1775615083, -0.01667501114), \\
(\beta_{4,3}, \beta_{4,2}, \beta_{4,1}, \beta_{4,0}) &= (0.1136196868, -0.2288068737, 0.1280662186, -0.01463663423). \\
(\alpha_{5,3}, \alpha_{5,2}, \alpha_{5,1}, \alpha_{5,0}) &= (0.4361600987, -0.7807099185, 0.3949111394, -0.04310026949), \\
(\beta_{5,3}, \beta_{5,2}, \beta_{5,1}, \beta_{5,0}) &= (-0.02927362518, 0.1035214626, -0.07713820019, 0.00869738015). \\
(\alpha_{6,3}, \alpha_{6,2}, \alpha_{6,1}, \alpha_{6,0}) &= (-0.103417728, 0.1970116733, -0.1040239632, 0.009357940815), \\
(\beta_{6,3}, \beta_{6,2}, \beta_{6,1}, \beta_{6,0}) &= (0.1270270644, -0.1709639984, 0.05864273442, -0.005089805928).
\end{aligned}$$

C Model coefficients (K=12)

The K=12 model follows exactly the same structure:

$$a_k(S) = \alpha_{k,3}S^3 + \alpha_{k,2}S^2 + \alpha_{k,1}S + \alpha_{k,0}, \quad b_k(S) = \beta_{k,3}S^3 + \beta_{k,2}S^2 + \beta_{k,1}S + \beta_{k,0}.$$

The numerical coefficients are:

$$\begin{aligned}
(\alpha_{0,3}, \alpha_{0,2}, \alpha_{0,1}, \alpha_{0,0}) &= (-1.772176177, 0.9245489378, 0.7516676726, -0.05529461262). \\
(\alpha_{1,3}, \alpha_{1,2}, \alpha_{1,1}, \alpha_{1,0}) &= (-2.49929409, 4.721869783, -2.454064149, 0.218755174), \\
(\beta_{1,3}, \beta_{1,2}, \beta_{1,1}, \beta_{1,0}) &= (0.533459388, -0.951326985, 0.4711985594, -0.04366542151). \\
(\alpha_{2,3}, \alpha_{2,2}, \alpha_{2,1}, \alpha_{2,0}) &= (1.483598003, -2.050290968, 0.7349365604, -0.06222441352), \\
(\beta_{2,3}, \beta_{2,2}, \beta_{2,1}, \beta_{2,0}) &= (-0.4009906341, 0.7695080563, -0.4094909182, 0.0400544111). \\
(\alpha_{3,3}, \alpha_{3,2}, \alpha_{3,1}, \alpha_{3,0}) &= (-0.8312597449, 1.713106161, -0.9510759352, 0.08337486833), \\
(\beta_{3,3}, \beta_{3,2}, \beta_{3,1}, \beta_{3,0}) &= (0.2761185673, -0.3570976704, 0.1094932399, -0.005864635851). \\
(\alpha_{4,3}, \alpha_{4,2}, \alpha_{4,1}, \alpha_{4,0}) &= (0.4283161489, -0.5617153215, 0.1848010205, -0.01742369427), \\
(\beta_{4,3}, \beta_{4,2}, \beta_{4,1}, \beta_{4,0}) &= (0.11158131, -0.2254870284, 0.1265689344, -0.01450115612). \\
(\alpha_{5,3}, \alpha_{5,2}, \alpha_{5,1}, \alpha_{5,0}) &= (0.4352518846, -0.7786557718, 0.3936976231, -0.04298509755), \\
(\beta_{5,3}, \beta_{5,2}, \beta_{5,1}, \beta_{5,0}) &= (-0.02759227004, 0.1006256082, -0.07572916943, 0.008552866378). \\
(\alpha_{6,3}, \alpha_{6,2}, \alpha_{6,1}, \alpha_{6,0}) &= (-0.1005215687, 0.1918912862, -0.1014751591, 0.009099196828), \\
(\beta_{6,3}, \beta_{6,2}, \beta_{6,1}, \beta_{6,0}) &= (0.127230739, -0.1715318116, 0.05901932771, -0.005126861723). \\
(\alpha_{7,3}, \alpha_{7,2}, \alpha_{7,1}, \alpha_{7,0}) &= (0.2089198848, -0.3541733912, 0.1662596099, -0.0151465389), \\
(\beta_{7,3}, \beta_{7,2}, \beta_{7,1}, \beta_{7,0}) &= (-0.1265985829, 0.1835187684, -0.06874068232, 0.003865363263). \\
(\alpha_{8,3}, \alpha_{8,2}, \alpha_{8,1}, \alpha_{8,0}) &= (0.06662062666, -0.1334126209, 0.07085219384, -0.005369128007), \\
(\beta_{8,3}, \beta_{8,2}, \beta_{8,1}, \beta_{8,0}) &= (-0.02429762729, 0.03482962527, -0.01227436914, 0.0002523605365). \\
(\alpha_{9,3}, \alpha_{9,2}, \alpha_{9,1}, \alpha_{9,0}) &= (-0.1183050734, 0.2084115476, -0.1045199583, 0.01129379838), \\
(\beta_{9,3}, \beta_{9,2}, \beta_{9,1}, \beta_{9,0}) &= (0.01383181327, -0.04286327207, 0.03214079939, -0.004993278549). \\
(\alpha_{10,3}, \alpha_{10,2}, \alpha_{10,1}, \alpha_{10,0}) &= (0.1066912438, -0.1862507973, 0.08846760601, -0.006903275876), \\
(\beta_{10,3}, \beta_{10,2}, \beta_{10,1}, \beta_{10,0}) &= (-0.08602733797, 0.1167377848, -0.04048654924, 0.003220730035). \\
(\alpha_{11,3}, \alpha_{11,2}, \alpha_{11,1}, \alpha_{11,0}) &= (-0.0054949113, -0.005384373793, 0.009413105568, -0.001139519132), \\
(\beta_{11,3}, \beta_{11,2}, \beta_{11,1}, \beta_{11,0}) &= (0.07974244487, -0.1460031712, 0.07428425937, -0.007114337614). \\
(\alpha_{12,3}, \alpha_{12,2}, \alpha_{12,1}, \alpha_{12,0}) &= (0.04631588598, -0.05576561212, 0.0136626437, -0.0003180838963), \\
(\beta_{12,3}, \beta_{12,2}, \beta_{12,1}, \beta_{12,0}) &= (0.04609537973, -0.08292999565, 0.04040825286, -0.0031099247).
\end{aligned}$$

Disclosures

The author declares no conflicts of interest.

Code and Data Availability

The code and data used to reproduce the experiments reported in this study are available in the Zenodo repository associated with this work: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18872691>. All synthetic test images used in the experiments can be regenerated from the scripts provided in the repository.

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